

ASYMMETRIC EFFECTS OF TAX POLICY ON PRIVATE INVESTMENT IN NIGERIA, GHANA AND SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the asymmetric effects of tax policy on private investment in Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa using annual data covering the period 1981 to 2024. The analysis was anchored on the Keynesian (1936) theory of fiscal policy effects. To capture potential nonlinear relationships, the nonlinear autoregressive distributed lag (NARDL) model was employed to examine both short-run and long-run asymmetries. The results revealed no evidence of a long-run relationship between tax policy and private investment in Ghana. In Nigeria, positive tax policy shocks exerted a stronger influence on private investment than negative shocks in both the short and long run. For South Africa, positive tax policy shocks had a more pronounced effect in the short run; however, in the long run, negative shocks generated a stronger response. Overall, the findings suggested that the long-run asymmetric effects of tax policy on private investment differed significantly across Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa, in line with the Keynesian (1936) proposition on fiscal policy effectiveness. Based on these results, the study recommended that policymakers in Nigeria maintain a stable and predictable tax environment to support long-term private investment planning. Furthermore, South Africa's tax system should be reassessed, with gradual reforms implemented to create a more investment-friendly environment over time.

Keywords: Asymmetric effects, fiscal policy, Ghana, NARDL model, Nigeria, private investment, South Africa, tax policy.

JEL Codes: E63, H20, H30.

1. INTRODUCTION

Private investment is widely recognized as a key driver of economic growth and global competitiveness, attracting policy attention worldwide (Sinevicienea & Railiene, 2015). In developing countries, where public investment alone is insufficient to sustain growth, private investment plays a critical role. Combey (2016) notes that African countries need to raise private investment to at least 23% of GDP to achieve sustainable growth. However, countries like Nigeria have struggled to meet this benchmark, with private investment shares in GDP at 54.6% (1985), 36.58% (1996), 24.11% (2006), 18.82% (2018), and 28.65% (2020) (World Bank Data, 2021). Ghana's figures were 6.99% (1996), 8.51% (2011), and 15.79% (2020), while South Africa's share remained below 20% from 1984 to 2021. The persistent low levels of private investment, despite policy interventions, threaten the prospects of higher economic growth in these sub-Saharan African economies, with structural constraints such as high fiscal deficits and inefficient fiscal sectors identified as major impediments (Comelli et al., 2023). To address these challenges, Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa have implemented various tax policy reforms. In Nigeria, the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP, 1986–1994) reduced

import taxes, provided relief to taxpayers, and introduced the Value Added Tax (VAT), while the Medium Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF, 1998) aimed to improve budget efficiency. South Africa's Growth, Employment, and Redistribution Strategy (GEAR, 1996) focused on lowering the overall tax burden, complemented by the MTEF (1997–2000). Ghana adopted the Economic Recovery Plan (ERP, 1983) and SAP (1986) to stabilise public finances, and the 1994 Investment Code ensured equitable treatment of foreign investors regarding taxes, prices, and access to foreign exchange.

These countries are also rich in natural resources, South Africa (gold), Nigeria (crude oil), and Ghana (gold and recently crude oil), making the effectiveness of policy interventions crucial for economic performance. Tax policies have been central to these efforts, yet their outcomes have varied. While the World Bank (2023) classifies South Africa as an upper-middle-income country with a strong industrial base, Nigeria and Ghana face challenges typical of lower-income economies.

Empirical evidence highlights the varied effects of taxation on investment and economic performance. Positive tax policy shocks in Nigeria have been found to exert stronger influence on private investment than negative shocks (Olaniyi, Onanuga, & Adekanmbi, 2025; Ukolobi & Oboro, 2021), while inefficient tax structures, high rates, and multiple taxation hinder SME growth and compliance (Sani & Ajayi, 2022). Additionally, tax policies affect welfare and the informal sector, which remains large in Nigeria (Olaleye, Tella, & Awolaja, 2022; Abdullahi, 2026). These findings underscore that the design and implementation of tax policies are pivotal in shaping private investment and economic growth outcomes.

Existing research largely examines tax policy and private investment within individual countries (Abdulkarim & Saidatulakmal, 2021; Awode, 2019; Chukwu et al., 2021; Senzu, 2019), leaving limited understanding of cross-country differences. Comparative studies like Babu, Pantaleo, and Ndanshau (2020) focus on smaller, less industrialized economies, limiting generalisability to larger, more complex economies such as Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa. This study addresses this gap by evaluating the asymmetric effects of tax policy on private investment across these three economies, offering insights into the dynamics of tax reforms and their investment implications.

Accordingly, the primary objective is to assess the asymmetric effects of tax policy on private investment across these three economies. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section Two reviews the relevant literature; Section Three outlines the methodology; Section Four presents and discusses the empirical results; and Section Five concludes with policy recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Literature

The Keynesian theory of fiscal policy (1936) advocates deficit financing, where government spending exceeds tax revenue, as a tool to stimulate economic activity during recessions. The rationale is that increased public investment combined with lower interest rates can boost aggregate demand. Expansionary fiscal policy, where spending surpasses revenue, is recommended in recessionary periods, while contractionary measures are suggested to stabilise the economy (Ncanywa & Masoga, 2018).

When government spending exceeds revenue, the shortfall is typically financed through domestic or foreign borrowing (Oche, Mah & Mongale, 2016). The approach aims to raise total demand, but excessive borrowing can increase interest rates, raising the cost of funds for investors and potentially causing a “crowd-out” effect (Ncanywa & Masoga, 2018). Conversely, central banks can stimulate investment by reducing interest rates, lowering financing costs and encouraging economic activity.

The Keynesian framework also notes that high public debt can undermine growth by raising taxes, reducing investment and consumption, and lowering employment and economic expansion (Ncanywa & Masoga, 2018). Moderate debt, however, may support growth if directed toward productive investment, increasing national income (Kamudia, 2015). Empirical studies indicate that higher government expenditure can both stimulate domestic investment (Biza, Kapingura, & Tsegaye, 2013) and crowd out private investment if it absorbs limited financial resources (Bamidele, 2020; Chinanuife, Eze & Nwodo, 2018; Huang, Panizza & Varghese, 2018).

Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa provide a useful context for examining these dynamics due to their differing economic structures. Nigeria is primarily an oil exporter, Ghana has a strong agricultural sector, and South Africa features a diversified economy with a robust industrial base. These differences allow for analysis of how tax policies interact with various sectors and structures, with implications for private investment.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Building on Keynes (1936), numerous studies have examined the relationship between tax policy and private investment. Muzurura and Sikwila (2018) analysed private fixed domestic investment in Zimbabwe (1998–2015), controlling for tax revenue, domestic savings, business uncertainty, and FDI inflows. Using OLS, the study found that tax revenue positively and significantly influenced investment, especially when directed toward productive public expenditure such as infrastructure, energy, and transport. Similarly, Uchime and Anichebe (2019) studied Nigeria (1995–2017) and reported a long-run relationship between taxation and domestic investment. While company income tax positively affected investment, personal income tax and GDP had no significant negative effect, and VAT showed no significant positive effect.

Other studies employed cointegration approaches. Tweneboah and Ndebugri (2018) examined corporate taxes in Ghana (1986–2011) using Johansen cointegration and found that corporate tax, interest rate, real exchange rate, and price level negatively affected private investment, while real GDP, public investment, and money supply had positive effects. Granger causality tests indicated a stronger causal influence from corporate tax to private investment than vice versa. Senzu (2019) extended this analysis with a VECM, confirming negative effects of corporate tax, interest rate, real exchange rate, and price level, and positive effects of real GDP, public investment, and money supply on private investment, with bidirectional causality between corporate tax and investment.

Studies using ARDL models also provide insights. Awode (2019) found that indirect tax, non-tax revenue, inflation, and capital expenditure positively influenced private investment in Nigeria (1987–2015), while domestic credit to the private sector had a negative effect. Abdulkarim and Saidatulakmal (2021) reported that direct taxes constrained private investment, whereas indirect taxes promoted it (1980–2017).

Babu, Pantaleo, and Ndanshau (2020) applied a one-step Difference GMM estimator for SSA countries in the EAC and SADC regions, showing that corporate income tax and VAT negatively affected investment, while real interest rates were a key determinant. Chukwu et al. (2021) found in Nigeria (1986–2019) that private investment Granger-caused tax revenue, while oil revenue positively influenced private investment, suggesting a crowd-in effect.

Despite these studies, there is no direct cross-country comparison of tax policy impacts on private investment in Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa. Existing research mainly focuses on individual countries or smaller SSA economies with weaker industrial bases, limiting generalisability (Babu, Pantaleo & Ndanshau, 2020). This study addresses this gap by comparing the effects of tax policy on private investment across the three economies, providing insights into how different economic structures interact with fiscal measures.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical foundation of this study is rooted in the Keynesian theory of fiscal policy (Keynes, 1936), which posits that government fiscal actions, particularly taxation and public expenditure, play a central role in influencing aggregate demand and investment behaviour. Within this framework, tax policy affects private investment primarily through its impact on the cost of capital and expected profitability. Higher taxes reduce after-tax returns and discourage investment, while tax reductions increase retained earnings and stimulate investment activity.

Beyond this direct effect, tax policy also operates through important transmission channels. It influences investor confidence, particularly in environments characterised by policy uncertainty, where frequent or unpredictable tax changes may discourage long-term investment planning. In addition, tax compliance and administrative efficiency affect the effective tax burden faced by firms, thereby shaping their investment decisions. Sectoral differences may also matter, as capital-intensive industries tend to be more sensitive to tax changes than others. However, the response of private investment to tax policy changes may not be symmetric. Firms often react differently to increases and decreases in taxes due to factors such as adjustment costs, uncertainty, and the irreversible nature of investment decisions. For instance, an increase in taxes may lead to an immediate contraction in investment, whereas a tax reduction may not generate a proportionate increase if firms remain cautious due to macroeconomic instability or weak policy credibility. In developing economies such as Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa, structural constraints, including imperfect capital markets and fiscal imbalances, can further amplify these asymmetric responses. As a result, positive and negative tax policy shocks may exert differing short-run and long-run effects on private investment.

Given these considerations, a linear modelling approach may be inadequate to capture the true nature of the relationship between tax policy and private investment. This study therefore adopts the nonlinear autoregressive distributed lag (NARDL) model, which allows for the decomposition of tax policy into positive and negative changes and enables the estimation of their distinct dynamic effects on private investment. This theoretical underpinning provides the basis for the empirical specification of the NARDL model used in this study.

3.2 Model Specification

This study employs the Nonlinear Autoregressive Distributed Lag (NARDL) model because the variables are of mixed integration order, $I(0)$ and $I(1)$, as confirmed by the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin (KPSS) tests. NARDL offers advantages over the traditional Error Correction Model (ECM) by allowing joint testing of dynamic cointegration and asymmetries in the variables, while distinguishing between linear and nonlinear cointegration (Ali, Shan, Wang, & Amin, 2018). The objective of this study is to evaluate the asymmetric effects of tax policy on private investment. Unlike standard ARDL models, which assume symmetric impacts of independent variables on the dependent variable (Fousekis, Katrakilidis & Trachanas, 2016), NARDL accommodates both symmetric and asymmetric effects. It is also more efficient in estimating short- and long-run coefficients by incorporating long-run dynamics and distributed lags within a single cointegration framework (Arize, Malindretos, & Igwe, 2017; Ekeocha, Penzin & Ogbuabor, 2020). Following the theoretical framework, private investment is modelled as a function of tax policy. Consistent with the Keynesian perspective, tax policy influences investment decisions through its effects on the cost of capital and expected returns. The baseline functional relationship is specified as:

$$PI_i = f(TXR) \dots \dots \dots [1]$$

Where, PI represents private investment, TXR denotes tax policy (proxied by tax revenue); *i* refers to country (Nigeria, Ghana, South Africa); and *t* denotes time.

A generic form of the NARDL model (p, q_1, \dots, q_k) is:

$$y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 t + \sum_{i=1}^p \varphi_i y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=0}^{qt} \beta_{j,ij} x_{j,t-i} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots [2]$$

Where, ε_t =innovations; α_0 =constant term; $\alpha_1, \varphi_i, \beta_{j,ij}$ = the coefficients of linear trend, lags of y_t , and lags of the *k* regressors, respectively and $x_{j,t}$ for $j = 1, \dots k$. To capture the potential asymmetric effects of tax policy, the nonlinear autoregressive distributed lag (NARDL) model proposed by Shin, Yu, and Greenwood-Nimmo (2014) is employed. The NARDL framework allows tax policy to be decomposed into positive and negative partial sums, representing increases and decreases in tax policy, respectively. Accordingly, the NARDL bounds test based on Equation [2] is specified as follows:

$$\Delta PI_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \phi_1 \Delta PI_{i,t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta_i^+ \Delta TXR_{i,t-i}^+ + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta_i^- \Delta TXR_{i,t-i}^- + \rho PI_{i,t-1} + \varphi_1^+ TXR_{i,t-1}^+ + \varphi_1^- TXR_{i,t-1}^- + \mu_t \dots \dots \dots [3]$$

$\phi_1, \delta_i^+, \delta_i^-$ = short-run coefficients; $\rho, \varphi_i^+, \varphi_i^-$ = long-run coefficients with asymmetric terms; and μ_t = disturbance term accounting for omitted variables.

The NARDL bounds test relies on the F-statistic, which follows a non-standard distribution. The cointegration decision is interpreted as follows: (i) if the computed F-statistic is below the lower bound, the null hypothesis is not rejected, indicating no long-run asymmetric relationship between tax policy and private investment; (ii) if the F-statistic lies between the lower and upper bounds, the results are inconclusive; and (iii) if the F-statistic exceeds the upper bound, it indicates the existence of a long-run asymmetric relationship between tax policy and private investment.

To test for nonlinearity, this study proceeded by dividing (i) the negative of the coefficients of positive independent variables (φ_i^+) by the coefficients of private investment (ρ); and (ii) dividing the negative of the coefficients of negative independent variables (φ_i^-) by the coefficients of private investment (ρ) and (iii) testing the hypotheses: $H_0: \frac{-(\varphi_i^+)}{\rho} = \frac{-(\varphi_i^-)}{\rho}$ and $H_A: \frac{-(\varphi_i^+)}{\rho} \neq \frac{-(\varphi_i^-)}{\rho}$. If H_0 is rejected, it means there is long-run asymmetry.

Adedeji, Ahmed and Muhammed (2018), and Qamruzzaman, Karim and Wei (2019) extended the NARDL model to include the asymmetric short-run dynamics by estimating an asymmetric error correction model (AECM) derived from the conventional ARDL as specified below:

$$\Delta PI_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \phi_1 \Delta PI_{i,t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta_i^+ \Delta TXR_{i,t-i}^+ + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta_i^- \Delta TXR_{i,t-i}^- + \sigma ECT_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots \dots \dots [4]$$

Where, ECT = error correction term; and σ = the speed of adjustment.

The error correction model (ECM) measures the speed at which the system returns to long-run equilibrium following a short-run shock. The coefficient of the error correction term, δ , must be negative and statistically significant to confirm adjustment toward the long-run asymmetric equilibrium (Pesaran, Shin & Smith, 2001).

When the null hypothesis of symmetry is rejected, asymmetric dynamic multipliers are estimated for positive and negative changes in the explanatory variables. These multipliers capture the effects of increases and decreases in tax policy, illustrating how private investment

adjusts to a new long-run equilibrium after shocks. This adjustment process can be expressed as follows:

$$m_h^+ = \sum_{j=0}^h \frac{\partial PI_{i,t+j}}{\partial TR_{i,t}^+} ; m_h^- = \sum_{j=0}^h \frac{\partial PI_{i,t+j}}{\partial TR_{i,t}^-} \dots \dots \dots [5]$$

For $h = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Where, If $h \rightarrow \infty$, then $m_h^+ \rightarrow \frac{-(\varphi_i^+)}{\rho}$ and $m_h^- \rightarrow \frac{-(\varphi_i^-)}{\rho}$, PI_i = private investments in Ghana, Nigeria and South Africa; $\partial TR_{i,t}^+$ = positive changes in tax revenue; $\partial TR_{i,t}^-$ = negative changes in tax revenue.

3.3 Estimation Procedure

To estimate the results of this study, unit root tests were conducted using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin (KPSS) methods to assess stationarity. Given that NARDL incorporates lagged values, the optimal lag length was determined prior to performing bounds tests to assess the existence of a long-run relationship among the variables. Once cointegration was established, both the short-run error correction model (ECM) and the long-run NARDL model were estimated. The model’s dynamic multipliers were subsequently calculated, and diagnostic tests, including normality, Ramsey’s RESET, heteroskedasticity, and serial correlation, were applied to evaluate goodness of fit and model robustness.

3.4 Data

This study uses annual data spanning 1981–2024, a period sufficient to capture fiscal booms and busts, changes in tax policy, regime shifts, political decisions, and variations in institutional quality that affect private investment in Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa. The dataset includes private investment (% of GDP) and tax revenue (% of GDP) as a proxy for tax policy. For Nigeria, private investment is coded as PIN and tax revenue as TXRN, sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the World Bank database. Ghanaian data comprise private investment (PIG) and tax revenue (TXRG), sourced from the Bank of Ghana (BOG) and the World Bank. South African data include private investment (PIS) and tax revenue (TXRS), obtained from the World Bank database.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics of the series are presented in Table 1. On average, private investment amounted to 29.65% in Nigeria, 9.43% in Ghana, and 13.72% in South Africa. Average tax revenue (used as a proxy for tax policy) was 13.78% in Nigeria, 14.83% in Ghana, and 24.24% in South Africa. The maximum observed private investment values were 72.67% (Nigeria, 1983), 24.78% (Ghana, 2005), and 18.07% (South Africa, 1983). Corresponding maximum tax revenues were 27.64% (Nigeria, 2000), 26.78% (Ghana, 2020), and 27.60% (South Africa, 2007). The minimum private investment values were 12.80% (Nigeria, 2013), -5.28% (Ghana, 2010), and 11.20% (South Africa, 2020), while the minimum tax revenue values were 5.53% (Nigeria, 2016), 7.38% (Ghana, 1992), and 19.75% (South Africa, 1983). Private investment in Nigeria exhibited the highest volatility (standard deviation = 14.34), followed by Ghana (6.12) and South Africa (1.71). Similarly, tax revenue was most volatile in Nigeria (6.25), compared to Ghana (5.17) and South Africa (2.08). Positive skewness of private investment in all three countries indicates a distribution dominated by higher values. Tax revenue distributions were positively skewed in Nigeria and Ghana, whereas South Africa showed a predominance of lower values. The Jarque-Bera test confirms that all series are normally distributed.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa

	PIN	TXRN	PIG	TXRG	PIS	TXRS
Mean	29.65	13.78	9.43	14.83	13.72	24.24
Maximum	72.67	27.64	24.78	26.78	18.07	27.60
Minimum	12.80	5.53	-5.28	7.38	11.20	19.75
Std. Dev.	14.34	6.25	6.12	5.17	1.71	2.08
Skewness	0.87	0.49	0.02	0.64	0.74	-0.15
Jarque-Bera	5.0601	2.29	0.01	2.82	3.61	1.53
Probability	0.07	0.32	0.99	0.24	0.1647	0.46

Source: Authors' Computations.

4.2 Pre-estimation Test

Table 2 presents the results of stationarity tests using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin (KPSS) methods. Unlike the ADF test, the KPSS test is more sensitive to certain deviations from stationarity, such as trends or level shifts, and was therefore used as a confirmatory test (Akeyede et al., 2016; Pfaff, 2008). The results show some discrepancies between the ADF and KPSS tests, except for tax revenue in Ghana, which is stationary at first difference, and private investment and tax revenue in South Africa, which are stationary at level and first difference, respectively. Overall, the findings confirm a mixed order of integration among the variables, with the highest integration occurring at the first-difference level, I(1). This property justifies the application of the NARDL approach in the subsequent analysis.

Table 2: Results of Stationarity/Unit Root Test

Vari able	ADF Test @ level	ADF Test @ 1 st Diff.	Order	KPSS Test @ level	KPSS Test @ 1 st Diff	Order
PIN	-3.67** [-2.94]	-	1(0)	0.73 [0.46]	0.08** [0.15]	1 (1)
TXRN	-2.18 [-2.94]	-6.04** [-2.94]	1(1)	0.21** [0.46]	-	1(0)
PIG	-2.59 [-2.94]	-4.27** [-2.95]	1(1)	0.15** [0.46]		1(0)
TXRG	-1.57 [-2.94]	-7.07** [-2.94]	1(1)	0.80 [0.46]	0.06** [0.46]	1(1)
PIS	-3.36** [-2.94]	-	1(0)	0.19** [0.46]	-	1(0)
TXRS	-2.49 [-2.94]	-6.81** [-2.94]	1(1)	0.73 [0.46]	0.25** [0.46]	1(1)

Source: Authors' Computations. Critical values @ 5% are in square brackets. ** indicates significance at 5% level of significance.

4.3 Optimal Lag Selection

Estimation of the NARDL model begins with the specification of a standard ARDL model. This step helps determine the appropriate lag structure to adequately capture the temporal dynamics and dependencies among the variables, thereby improving model specification and statistical inference. Based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), the optimal lag lengths selected were (4, 0, 0) for Nigeria, (2, 4) for Ghana, and (2, 1, 0) for South Africa.

4.4 Bounds Test for Cointegration

The results of the bounds test for cointegration between private investment and tax policy are presented in Table 3. The findings indicate the existence of a long-run relationship between private investment and tax policy in Nigeria and South Africa at the 5% level of significance. However, no evidence of a long-run relationship was found for Ghana. No long-run

relationship is observed, possibly because structural factors, policy credibility, and tax administration weaken the transmission of tax policy to private investment.

Table 3: Result of ARDL Bounds Test

Country	Test Statistic	Value	Significance Level	Critical Value I(0)	Critical Value I(1)
Nigeria	F Statistic	6.35	1%	5.15	6.36
			5%	3.79	4.85
			10%	3.17	4.14
Ghana	F Statistic	3.32	1%	4.94	5.58
			5%	3.62	4.16
			10%	3.02	3.51
South Africa	F Statistic	4.99	1%	5.15	6.36
			5%	3.79	4.85
			10%	3.17	4.14

Source: Authors' Computations.

4.5. Long-Run and Short-Run Results

The long-run and short-run results for Nigeria, as reported in Table 4, indicate that the error correction term (ECT) is statistically significant at 5% and has the expected negative sign. The ECT is approximately -0.64, suggesting that 64% of deviations of private investment from its equilibrium value are corrected within a year. In the short run, PIN(-1) negatively affects its current value, while TXRN_POS exerts a negative and statistically significant effect on private investment. In the long run, TXRN_POS also has a negative and significant impact, whereas TXRN_NEG shows a negative but non-significant effect. The coefficient of determination indicates that 93% of the variation in private investment is explained by the explanatory variables.

For Ghana, a first-difference ARDL model was implemented for the short run due to the absence of cointegration. As shown in Table 4, the results reveal that, except for D(TXRG(-4)), the other short-run coefficients are not statistically significant. The model explains about 52% of the variation in private investment, suggesting moderate explanatory power.

In the case of South Africa, the short-run results in Table 4 indicate that PIS(-1) negatively affects its current value, whereas D(TXRS_POS) has a positive and statistically significant effect on private investment. The ECT is -0.245 and statistically significant, indicating that approximately 24% of deviations from equilibrium are corrected within a year. The long-run results suggest that both TXRS_POS and TXRS_NEG have positive but statistically insignificant effects on private investment.

Table 4: Results of Long-Run and Short-Run Models

Country	Panel	Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Nigeria	Long-Run	TXRN_POS	-0.66	0.16	-3.95	0.00
		TXRN_NEG	-0.09	0.15	-0.62	0.53
Nigeria	Short-Run	C	32.71	8.96	3.65	0.00
		PIN(-1)*	-0.63	0.16	-3.96	0.00
		TXRN_POS**	-0.42	0.13	-3.09	0.00
		TXRN_NEG**	-0.06	0.09	-0.64	0.52
		D(PIN(-1))	0.27	0.14	1.91	0.06
		D(PIN(-2))	-0.12	0.13	-0.90	0.37
		D(PIN(-3))	0.27	0.14	1.97	0.05
		ECM(-1)	-0.63	0.13	-4.79	0.00
Model Stats			R ² = 0.93; F-Stat Prob = 0.00; DW = 2.02			

Ghana	Short-Run	D(PIG(-1))	0.10	0.17	0.58	0.56
		D(PIG(-2))	-0.32	0.17	-1.85	0.07
		D(TXRG)	-0.00	0.29	-0.01	0.99
		D(TXRG(-1))	-0.37	0.28	-1.31	0.20
		D(TXRG(-2))	-0.12	0.29	-0.42	0.67
		D(TXRG(-3))	-0.28	0.28	-1.00	0.32
		D(TXRG(-4))	0.58	0.28	2.05	0.04
		C	0.12	0.86	0.14	0.88
Model Stats		R ² = 0.52; F-Stat Prob = 0.00; DW = 1.75				
South Africa	Long-Run	TXRS_POS	0.80	0.44	1.82	0.07
		TXRS_NEG	1.02	0.58	1.74	0.09
South Africa	Short-Run	C	2.39	1.12	2.12	0.04
		PIS(-1)*	-0.24	0.07	-3.34	0.00
		TXRS_POS(-1)	0.19	0.10	1.91	0.06
		TXRS_NEG**	0.25	0.14	1.75	0.08
		D(PIS(-1))	0.21	0.14	1.47	0.14
		D(TXRS_POS)	0.55	0.19	2.86	0.00
		ECM(-1)	-0.24	0.06	-3.98	0.00
		Model Stats	R ² = 0.82; F-Stat Prob = 0.00; DW = 2.10			

Source: Authors' Computations.

4.6. Wald Test for Asymmetry

Table 5 presents the Wald test results for long-run and short-run asymmetry. A p-value below 5% leads to rejection of the null hypothesis of no asymmetry. The results indicate an asymmetric effect of tax policy on private investment in both the short and long run for Nigeria and South Africa. In contrast, Ghana shows no evidence of asymmetry. Consequently, a NARDL model is applied for Nigeria and South Africa, while a linear ARDL model is used for Ghana.

Table 5: Results of Wald Test for Asymmetry

Country	Test Statistics (F-Statistic / P-Value)	Decision
Nigeria	WLR: 40.72** / 0.00	Asymmetric
	WSR: 11.51** / 0.00	
Ghana	WLR: 0.98 / 0.32	No Asymmetry
	WSR: 0.98 / 0.32	
South Africa	WLR: 2.18** / 0.00	Asymmetric
	WSR: 9.47** / 0.00	

Source: Authors' Computations. W_{LR} = Wald test for long-run asymmetry; W_{SR} = Wald test for short-run asymmetry. ** implies significance at 5% level.

4.7. Dynamic Multipliers

Figure 2 illustrates how private investment adjusts to new long-run equilibrium following positive and negative unit shocks to tax policy. Positive shocks are shown by the thick solid black line, negative shocks by the thick broken black line, and the asymmetry (the difference between responses) is represented by the thick broken red line. The thin broken red lines indicate the 95% confidence interval.

Figure 2a shows private investment rising with positive shocks and falling with negative shocks. The asymmetric plot deviates from zero toward the solid black line, indicating that positive tax shocks have a stronger impact on private investment than negative shocks, both

short and long term. The 95% confidence interval excludes zero, confirming statistical significance and asymmetry, consistent with Table 4. Positive tax shocks have a stronger effect on private investment, indicating that tax increases more strongly influence firms' decisions. Higher taxes raise the cost of capital and reduce expected returns, discouraging investment. In contrast, tax reductions may have a weaker effect due to policy uncertainty and adjustment frictions. This finding aligns with Awode (2019) but contrasts with Tweneboah and Ndebugri (2018), who reported adverse effects of tax policy on investment.

Figure 2a: Dynamic Multiplier Graph for Nigeria

The results (Figure 2b) show that private investment responds positively to positive tax policy shocks and negatively to negative shocks. In the short run, the asymmetric plot trends toward the thick solid black line, indicating that positive shocks have a stronger immediate effect on private investment than negative shocks. Over the long run, however, negative shocks exert a greater impact, suggesting that adverse tax policy shocks influence private investment more significantly over time. Positive tax shocks have a pronounced short-run effect, suggesting firms respond quickly to tax increases due to higher costs. Negative shocks have stronger long-run effects, reflecting gradual improvements in investor confidence and profitability expectations over time. These findings are consistent with studies by Senzu (2019), Abdulkarim and Saidatulakamal (2021), and Babu, Pantaleo, and Ndanshau (2020), which highlight the positive effect of tax policy on private investment, though they contrast with the results of Awode (2019). The 95% confidence interval lies outside the zero bounds, confirming the statistical significance of the asymmetry and corroborating the results presented in Table 4.

Figure 2b: Dynamic Multiplier Graph for South Africa

4.8. Diagnostic Tests

The diagnostic tests presented in Table 6 reveal the appropriateness of the models estimated for Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa. In each case, the results of the Jarque-Bera test show that the residuals are normally distributed. The Ramsey Reset test reveals that the models are well

specified. The LM test confirms the absence of autocorrelation while the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test suggests no evidence of heteroscedasticity.

Table 6: Results of Diagnostic Tests

Diagnostic Test	Statistic	Nigeria	Ghana	South Africa
Ramsey RESET	t-Statistic	0.16 (0.86)	0.37 (0.71)	1.38 (0.17)
	F-Statistic	0.02 (0.86)	0.14 (0.71)	1.91 (0.17)
LM Serial Correlation	F-Statistic	1.43 (0.25)	0.74 (0.48)	0.83 (0.44)
	Obs*R-squared	6.67 (0.15)	1.64 (0.43)	2.00 (0.36)
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroscedasticity	Scaled explained SS	4.88 (0.55)	2.94 (0.89)	4.45 (0.48)
	F-Statistic	1.79 (0.13)	0.86 (0.54)	0.91 (0.48)
	Obs*R-squared	9.77 (0.13)	6.39 (0.49)	4.76 (0.44)
Jarque-Bera	Statistic (p-value)	2.28 (0.31)	0.05 (0.97)	4.09 (0.12)

Source: Authors' Computations.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study evaluated the asymmetric effects of tax policy on private investment in Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa from 1981 to 2024 using the nonlinear ARDL model. Though some studies have been carried out on the relationship between tax policy and private investment, the focus has been on individual economies. Despite that few studies undertook a comparative study of some countries, the economies examined have a smaller and a less industrialized and economic structure and size (with varying implications on tax and private investment) compared to Nigeria, Ghana and South Africa. This study thus contributes to the debate on tax policy-private investment nexus in a unique pattern by undertaking a comparative study of Nigeria, Ghana and South Africa. The study found no long-run relationship between tax policy and private investment in Ghana. In Nigeria, the study found that positive tax policy shocks weighed more on private investment than adverse tax policy shocks, both in the short and long run. The result for South Africa revealed that in the short run, the effect of positive tax policy shocks on private investment was more pronounced than negative shocks. However, the magnitude of the response of private investment to negative tax policy shocks became stronger in the long run. These findings are in line with the Keynesian theory of fiscal policy effects (1936) which proposes a relationship between tax policy and private investment. On the basis of this, the study concludes that the asymmetric effects of tax policy on private investment in the long-run are statistically different in Nigeria, Ghana and South Africa.

In view of the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been made: First, it is essential for Nigerian policymakers to maintain a stable and predictable tax environment. Stability will encourage long-term investment planning by private entities. Second, the negative long-term effect of tax policy on private investment in South Africa necessitates a re-evaluation of current tax policies. It is recommended to implement gradual tax reforms aimed at creating a more investment-friendly environment over time. This could include reducing tax burdens, simplifying the tax code, and ensuring a more stable fiscal policy to prevent long-term disincentives for private investment. Third, targeted short-term tax incentives can be introduced to attract immediate private investment in Ghana, which could subsequently stimulate broader economic activity. These short-term tax incentives include tax holidays, reducing corporate tax rates, offering tax credits, and exemptions on import duties. Fourth, for more effective fiscal policies in the future, further research should be conducted to understand the specific dynamics and constraints that prevent a long-term relationship between tax policy and private investment in Ghana.

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